

Conformations of Substituents in *ortho*-Substituted Anisoles and Conjugative Interactions of Substituents in *para*-Substituted Anisoles. A Study from Dipole Moments

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THOUGH the methoxy group of an *ortho*-substituted anisole is known to assume an orientation in which the *O*-methyl is away from the *ortho*-substituent¹⁻³, more information can be obtained on the molecular

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conformation of *ortho*-substituted anisoles from a study of their dipole moments. The dipole moments can also throw light on the existing steric, polar and field effects of the *ortho*-substituent. In the case of *para*-substituted anisoles, the dipole moments can indicate interactions that occur between the *para*-substituents through conjugation. These possibilities prompted us to analyse the dipole moments of some *ortho*- and *para*-substituted anisoles. The relevant data are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DIPOLE MOMENTS OF *ortho*- AND *para*-SUBSTITUTED ANISOLES

Sl. no.	Anisole	μ_{obs} (D)	μ_{Calcd} (D)	
			For free rotation*	For conformation(1)
1.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	1.10 1.06 ^a	1.36	1.03
2.	<i>o</i> -F	2.33 2.31 ^b	1.77	2.48
3.	<i>o</i> -Cl	2.49 2.50 ^b	1.87	2.61
4.	<i>o</i> -Br	2.47 2.47 ^b	1.86	2.59
5.	<i>o</i> -COCH ₃	4.02 ^a	3.07	
6.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	1.22 1.21 ^a	1.21	
7.	<i>p</i> -F	2.04 2.04 ^c	2.13	
8.	<i>p</i> -Cl	2.30 2.26 ^d	2.25	
9.	<i>p</i> -Br	2.29 2.26 ^e	2.23	
10.	<i>p</i> -I	2.16 2.14 ^f	2.07	
11.	<i>p</i> -COCH ₃	3.55 3.56 ^g	3.33	

*For free rotation of both groups. ^aRef. 4. ^bRef. 5. ^cRef. 6. ^dRef. 7. ^eRef. 8. ^fRef. 9. ^gRef. 10.

Though the dipole moments of all the compounds listed in Table 1 are recorded in the literature⁴⁻¹⁰ (determined by different workers under different conditions) they are redetermined in all cases except one to have values obtained under the same conditions. The apparatus used for the determination of dipole moments and the method of calculation were described earlier¹¹. All measurements were made in benzene solution at 30 ± 0.05°.

For calculation of dipole moments from group moments¹¹, the dipole angles of the methoxy group¹² and acetyl group¹³ were taken as 75° and 125°, respectively. The group moments of CH₃, F, Cl, Br, I, OCH₃ and COCH₃ were taken as those¹² of toluene (0.37 D), fluorobenzene (1.43), chlorobenzene (1.57), bromobenzene (1.55), iodobenzene (1.36), anisole (1.25) and acetophenone (2.90 D), respectively.

In column 4 of Table 1 are given the dipole moments calculated for free rotation of the substituent groups. It may be seen that these values differ considerably from the observed dipole moments in the case of *ortho*-substituted anisoles, indicating absence of free rotation of the methoxy

group. Conformation 1 seems to be the most probable for compounds sl. nos. 1-4, the methoxy group being coplanar with the benzene ring. This view gets support from the fact that the earlier studies from ¹³C nmr¹ and crystallographic data² indicate such *O*-methyl orientation in *ortho*-substituted anisoles.

For *o*-methylanisole and *o*-halogenoanisoles (sl. nos. 2-4), the observed dipole moments are close to the values calculated for conformation 1, though the agreement cannot be said to be good. Presumably these differences arise from mutual induction¹⁵ of the adjacent *ortho*-groups.

For *o*-acetylanisole the observed dipole moment (4.02 D) is not much different from the calculated value (4.14 D) for conformation 2 (*s-trans*). The difference of 0.12 D between the two values suggests that the CH₃CO and OCH₃ groups are not perfectly coplanar with the benzene ring as is assumed in the calculation. The probability is that the CH₃CO group is slightly tilted from the plane of the benzene ring. Though conformation 3 (*s-cis*) can also be considered for this compound, the dipole moment calculated for this conformation is 3.14 D and hence 3 can be excluded from the consideration.

The four *p*-halogeno compounds (sl. nos. 7-10) show an interesting behaviour. The calculated moment of the fluoro compound is higher than the experimental moment. For the chloro, bromo and iodo compounds the reverse is the case. The same trend is observed¹⁴ in the dipole moments of *para*-halogenoanilines and *para*-halogen-*N,N*-dimethylanilines.

The observed dipole moments of *p*-chloro, *p*-bromo and *p*-iodo compounds are slightly but significantly higher than the calculated values due to *d*-orbital resonance (4); Cl, Br and I can expand their valence shells by utilising the vacant *d*-orbitals, when there is a powerful electron-releasing group in the *para*-position^{12,14,16}. The ability to participate

in *d*-orbital resonance increases in the order, Cl < Br < I. This is also reflected in the dipole moments of

of *p*-chloro-, *p*-bromo- and *p*-iodoanisoles. The *d*-orbital resonance is not possible for the fluoro compound, there being no vacant *d*-orbitals in its valence shell. The observed moment for this compound is less than the calculated moment because there is mutual opposition to electron-release (+*M* effect) by F and OCH₃ groups when they are *para* to each other.

For *p*-acetylanisole the observed and calculated dipole moments differ by more than 0.2 D indicating significant mesomeric interaction of the acetyl and methoxy groups.

References

1. K. S. DHAMI and J. B. STOTHERS, *Can J. Chem.*, 1966, **44**, 2855.
2. I. I. SCHUSTER, M. PARVEZ and A. J. FREYER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1988, **53**, 5819.
3. V. BALIAH and T. CHELLATHURAI, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1989, **101**, 311.
4. J. W. WILLIAMS, *Physik. Z.*, 1928, 683.
5. W. F. ANZILOTTI and B. C. CURRAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 607.
6. N. J. LEONARD and L. E. SUTTON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1564.
7. E. BERGMAN and L. ENGEL, *Phys. Z. (B)*, 1931, **15**, 85.
8. C. P. SMYTH and W. S. WALLS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 3230.
9. E. BERGMAN and M. TSCHUDNOWSKY, *Z. Phys. Chem (B)*, 1932, **17**, 107.
10. A. E. LUTSKII, *Zh. Fiz. Khim.*, 1949, **23**, 361.
11. V. BALIAH and K. GANAPATHY, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, **59**, 1784.
12. V. BALIAH and M. UMA, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, **19**, 455.
13. V. BALIAH and K. APARAJITHAN, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, **19**, 2117.
14. V. BALIAH and C. SRINIVASAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 217.
15. C. P. SMYTH, "Dielectric Behaviour and Structure", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1955, p. 687.
16. L. GOODMAN and L. J. FROLEN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1959, **30**, 1361.